

DEMOCRATIC CULTURE AND GOOD GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE.

AMAH MACLEAN WILLIAMS

Department of History and International Studies

Akwa Ibom State University, Nigeria.

e-mail: amahwilliams@aksu.edu.ng

NSIDIBE AKPAN USORO

Department of Sociology and Anthropology

University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria

nsidibeusoro@uniuyo.edu.ng

&

ESTHER KINGSLEY EGEMBA

Department of Sociology and Anthropology

University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria

esther_ebong@yahoo.com.

Abstract

In the contemporary world, democracy remains the most preferred form of government and the basis for fulfilling government responsibilities to the citizens. Hence, Nigerians home and abroad expressed Joy and great expectations as President Olusegun Obasanjo was sworn in as an elected President on 29 May 1999 marking the return to Democracy and the end of military rule in Africa's most populous nation. Nigerians expected that the return to Democracy will usher in an era of justice, fairness, inclusiveness, accountability in the conduct of the affairs of the nation, and massive infrastructural development and improvement in the welfare of the Nigerian people. Twenty years down the line, these expectations seem not to have been met, resulting in many threats to Nigeria's democratic experience. It is therefore an issue of fundamental importance how to consolidate democracy in Nigeria. Hence, this paper brought to light the inseparable linkage between a democratic polity and a regime of good governance. Using secondary data, the paper analyses the collapse of democratic administrations in Nigeria since independence and threats to the democratic experience of the fourth Republic. The findings of this paper showed that strengthening Democracy in Nigeria goes beyond the periodic conduct of elections. Rather, entrenching a regime of Good Governance is inevitable to the consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria.

Keywords: Culture, Democracy, Good Governance, Consolidation of Democracy

1. Introduction

In a plural society like Nigeria with over 250 ethnic groups as evidenced by the presence of different languages with diverse interests, democracy remains the best

form of Government to help Nigeria find meaning in its journey as a nation. This has been proven beyond doubt as the worst democratic administration is better than the best military regime. This is so because democracy provides a platform for inclusiveness where the people can participate in governance through their elected representatives and their voices are heard. The rights of citizens are also better guaranteed in a democracy than in other forms of government. On the other hand, the government remains committed to fulfilling the aspirations of the people knowing that power belongs to the people and any government that does not fulfill its responsibilities to citizens can be withdrawn in line with relevant laws.

Nigeria's first democratic experience lasted for just six years while the second lasted only four years. Until 1999, the greater part of Nigeria's post-colonial period witnessed the military dominating the Nigerian political space and exercising actual rulership of the nation. The period of military rulership was marked by frustration, flagrant violation of rights of citizens, stunted political and economic growth, massive corruption, indiscipline, moral decadence, ethnic rivalry occasioned by the suppression of one ethnic group by the other, and the silencing of dissenting voices. With the return to democracy in 1999, Nigerians expected that the societal ills associated with the military regimes will cease to exist and the reign of democracy will usher in a massive improvement in the quality of life of the peoples of Nigeria.

Whereas twenty years later, various democratic administrations are still attempting to meet the aspirations of Nigerians, it is instructive to note that these expectations, though not fully met yet, can only be realized over time if democracy endures in Nigeria. It is expedient to also remain conscious of the fact that though democracy remains the best form of government for any nation, it is also perhaps the most difficult to entrench and consolidate especially in a society where corruption, greed, and avarice has been firmly rooted due to long years of military rule. As aptly stated by Diamond (1992: 30), "It is one thing to get Democracy, it is another thing, often more difficult, to keep it, to consolidate it, to breath real life and meaning into it and to make it endure". It has therefore become fundamentally important to think of ways of consolidating Democracy in Nigeria and good governance remains one of the surest paths towards sustainable democracy. Hence, in establishing this fact, this paper takes a cursory look at the travails of democracy in Nigeria linking the absence of good governance to the failure of every democratic dispensation before 1999 and identifies some major threats to democracy in Nigeria. While establishing that Democracy in Nigeria can only be consolidated through Good Governance, the paper further explains and recommend for implementation the basic ingredients of Good Governance necessary for the consolidation of Democracy

2. Methodology

This paper derives its data for analysis from secondary sources of data collection. It adopts a documentary method of data analysis which involves retrieving and

analysing information from public documents such as official position papers, Newspapers, memoirs, Journals and textbooks. Evidence gathered will be corroborated to check for internal and external consistency and synthesis. The functional (narrative) and causal (analytic) approaches will be used simultaneously to draw conclusions. The method of data analysis in this paper will be largely historical and descriptive.

3. Conceptual Issues

To get a clear understanding of the issues discussed in this paper, it is instructive to clarify key concepts used in this work.

- a) A foremost anthropologists, Edward Tylor (1971) describes culture as that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, arts, morals, laws, customs and every other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society(Modo,2016).Culture is a holistic description of man and his activities. The ideas, belief system, products of man's inventions, the influence of man on social, spiritual, economic and politics in which democracy and good governance are key issues fall within the purview of culture.

Usoro and Ekong (2016) sees culture as a wide and multi-faceted concept that is very difficult to deal with in its entirety in a single study.

- b) **Democracy:** In his famous Gettysburg speech, the 16th President of the United States of America, Abraham Lincoln referred to Democracy as the Government of the People, by the people and for the people(Herskovits,1979: 332).This has over time become a common definition of Democracy. It is instructive to note that the word Democracy is not admissible of a precise definition as the term is generic and imprecise. While it is difficult to define democracy with one precise and all-encompassing definition, there exists some kind of consensus among scholars what constitutes the basic ingredients of genuine democracy. The Greek derivation of the term indicates that the term democracy meant rule by the people although the extent to which the people can govern vary tremendously from society to society. However, to a significant degree, a democratic government must rest on the consent of the governed and its policies must be responsive to their desires (Eminue, 2001:35).

Omotoso (2013:125) identifies freedom of expression of opinion on the management of public affairs, eligibility to vote and be voted for, free and fair elections, popular sovereignty, and respect for the will of the people as the basic ingredients of Democracy. Within the democratic setup, the government recognizes that the wellbeing of the citizens is its fundamental responsibility, power belongs to the people while those who occupy political offices are merely agents of the people with the mandate to act on their behalf. Hence, democracy does not accommodate

arbitrariness in the exercise of power since those in authority are accountable to the people (Anugwom, 2000:63).

The definition of democracy and what it entails is as diverse as there are scholars in the field, however, having identified the basic ingredients of Democracy this paper adopts the definition given by Eminiue (2001:35); that democracy is a form of government organized in accordance with the principle of Popular Sovereignty, Political and Economic Equality, Popular Consultation and Majority Rule.

- c) **Good governance:** According to the United Nations Development Programme working document on Governance for Sustainable Human Development published in 1997, 'Good governance refers to governing systems which are capable, responsive, inclusive, and transparent. Good Governance is inextricably linked to the sustenance of democracy it goes beyond articulating good policies and making big promises. It has to do with meeting the yearnings and aspirations of the people. Okon Uya (1999:5) sketched the ingredients of good governance to include;
- I. Implementing and institutionalizing the love for freedom and equality.
 - ii. Encouraging the freedom of dissent and respect for the individuality of each person
 - iii. 4Creation of an appropriate environment that enables the individual to free himself from the constraints of poverty, hunger, ill-health, coercion and control.
 - iv. Equality of all, the ruler and the ruled, before the law.
 - v. Equality of opportunity and access to quality education, medical attention and work.
 - vi. The creation of an ordered stable society that guarantees the security of lives and properties of individuals, inculcating a sense of civic responsibility, an attitude of service and trusteeship, tolerance of other people's opinion and interest, impartial and objective service.
 - vii. The emergence of selfless, discipline, dedicated, patriotic, honest, and highly motivated leadership free from religious bigotry, ethnic chauvinism and the tendency to personalize rulership and power.
 - viii. A deliberate move towards the creation of a society bound together by shared sentiments and outlook, an overall commitment to even and rapid development of the human elements within the polity (Uya, 1999:5).

This paper fully adopts, Uya's sketch of the ingredients of Good Governance which must not lack in Nigeria's democratic space if the leadership of the Nation is serious about consolidating Democracy in Nigeria. There must be a total overhaul in the leadership style of those who occupy public office. An era of justice, respect for human rights, provision of basic amenities, transparency in doing government business, inclusiveness in governance, sound economic policies geared towards

alleviating poverty amongst the people, must be ushered in. In all, good governance entails meeting the aspirations of the people, satisfying their desire for it is for it was for this reason the governance was established in the first place.

Consolidation of democracy: The Consolidation of Democracy is fully achieved in a Society when the ingredients of Democracy is well entrenched such that democratic norms become the rule rather than the exception. In a polity where democracy is fully consolidated, the leaders and the led, see democratic norms as a way of life and cannot compromise the violation of democratic principles at whatever cost. Salawu and Hassan (2011:30) see the Consolidation of Democracy as a level of democratic maturity where reactionary forces from within or without can no longer threaten or truncate it.

Also writing the concept of Consolidation of Democracy, Ajayi and Ojo (2014:115) note that it is the process of entrenching broad and deep legitimization of democratic norms such that both the leaders and the people believe that the democratic system is better for the society than any other realistic alternative they can imagine.

Omotola aptly summed up as follows;

democratic consolidation must be more than a commitment to democracy in the abstract; it must also involve a shared normative or behavioural commitment to the specific rules, values, attitudes and practices of a country's constitutional system(Omotola, 2009:195).

4. Theoretical framework

In his book, *Why Men Rebel*, Robert Gurr (1970:15) propounds the theory of relative deprivation. This theory explains that collective dissatisfaction manifests as political violence. In other words, anger which mounts as a result of deprivation leads men to aggression and revolt. Explaining further, Gurr (1970:16) posits that a higher degree of frustration is proportional to greater political instability in a country. Relative Deprivation theory explains situations where citizens feel that they have been deprived of certain rights and privileges occasioned by the absence of good governance by those in authority. This inspires the people to get rid of the prevailing situation. In Gurr's definition of Relative Deprivation, the gap between the expectation of the citizens and reality creates a state of discontentment, frustration, hostility, insurgencies, revolutions and conflict. The magnitude of hostility is therefore determined by the gap between the expectation of the people and the reality (Gurr, 1970:17).

This theory is most suitable for this paper and better explains the threat facing democracy in Nigeria. In the growing face of discontentment amongst citizens and the rising wave of insecurity, if Good Governance is not fully entrenched at all levels

in the polity, whereby the people have a feeling of relative satisfaction and hope, Nigeria's twenty-three-year-old democratic experience is certainly at risk of collapsing.

5. The Travails of Democracy in Nigeria

One of the most significant contemporary political phenomena is the triumph of democracy as an honourific word. It is such that everyone even notorious dictators want to identify with democracy. The Soviet Union and its satellites had described themselves as people democracies. Even Fascist dictators like Mussolini and Hitler have found it vital to claim that they embodied democratic aspirations. Much more apt is the Democratic People's Republic of North Korea, an autocratic regime that describes itself as Democratic People's Republic. Hence, as of 1960 when Nigeria got independence from Britain, Democracy had gained wide acceptance as a form of government in the world. The British Colonizers, therefore, established Western-style democracy in Nigeria with the organization of the 1959 elections and subsequent handover to the elected representatives of the indigenous leaders who won the elections. That marked the beginning of democratic experience in Nigeria.

As reported by Oluwatosin for the Daily Times of 3rd May 1961, Nigerian nationalists, in their intense desire for independence, reached compromise without putting in place the basic requirements of Good Governance such as inclusiveness, issues of equal opportunity, proper sharing of the nation's wealth, the strategy of fighting corruption and so on. From the beginning, parties were formed along ethnic lines with the Northern NPC forming a coalition government with the mainly Eastern NCNC then the Western AG emerged as the opposition. The NPC-NCNC coalition was hostile to the AG opposition and this gave room for nepotism and corruption to thrive. The near absence of Justice as seen in the dismissal of the NCNC suit against the Federal Government on the authenticity of the 1963 Census further exacerbated the already precarious situation. Poor remuneration and welfare of workers led to the Nationwide strike called by the joint action committee of the Nigerian Trade Unions in June 1964. Corruption became the order of the day, crisis ensued in the Western Region and pockets of violence and insecurity took place across the Nation. Inspired by the rancorous situation across the Nation, a group of Majors based in Kaduna staged a coup on the night of 14-15 January 1966 which led to the assassination of the Federal Prime Minister, the Premiers of Western and Northern Regions, the Federal Minister of Finance, and top military and political office holders in the country. The coup plotters did not succeed in taking over the Government, because they failed to kill the head of the Army, Major General J.T. AguyiIrons, he and other surviving officers were able to put down the coup and restore normalcy. To them, the corrupt and terrified politicians handed over Power that signaled the failure and collapse of Nigeria's first attempt at democracy (Akinrinade, 2006:284).

Though military take-over was not justifiable for any reason, there is a sense in which Nigerians welcomed the action of the military in 1966. One can see the absence of

Good Governance in the first republic. The freedom of dissent was not guaranteed as seen by the suppression of leaders of the opposition Action Group (AG). Unequal access to education and health services, instability in the society which gave rise to insecurity, the absence of civic responsibility, lack of an attitude of service and trusteeship, intolerance of other people's opinion and interest, partial and biased public service were all signals that the first republic will soon collapse (Azeez, 2009:3). As seen in the theory of Relative Deprivation, collective dissatisfaction as a result of the absence of good governance led to resentment and violence across the country and the military, therefore, found cogent reasons to take over the government. Though the people could not revolt by themselves but were happy that the military was able to do so. Therefore, it could be safely concluded that if the politicians of the first republic, paid attention to the precepts of Good Governance, the first republic wouldn't have collapsed, rather democratic ideals would have been gradually entrenched.

Nigeria's second attempt at Democracy came with the implementation of the transition programmes of the Murtala Mohammed/Olusegun Obasanjo transition to civil rule programme by General Olusegun Obasanjo as head of state in 1979. After several preparatory activities and a series of elections ending with the presidential elections of 11 August 1979, the country returned to civilian government on 1st October 1979 after thirteen years of military rule with a presidential system of government operated on the American model.

With the Presidential system in place which gave immense power to the President unlike the British Parliamentary model of the first republic, the nation was bound to make a great advance if the President was courageous, clear-headed, decisive, dynamic, forthright and cares about the rudiments of Good Governance. According to Ojo, (2014:58), the action plan of the Shehu Shagari government rested on three principal programme which includes; Housing for the masses, Agricultural Revolution and Movement to the New Federal capital. However, the efforts put in the three major programmes of the regime did not produce commensurate positive results. Corruption, inefficiency and extravagant spending characterised the performances as in most other areas of public life. The squandermania of the regime was all the more reprehensible for occurring in the period of global oil glut which resulted in reduced income from petroleum. It is instructive to note that while the nation's external reserve stood at N2.5 billion at the beginning of the regime, the nation was over N20 billion in debt by the time that government was removed from office (Daily Times, January 1980). This was as a result of the great increase in imports, expensive overseas tours, ostentatious lifestyle, uncontrolled external borrowing and gross financial mismanagement and extravagant spending at both federal and state levels (Koonings and Kruijt, 2002:30)

In the midst of all these, workers and common people were queuing for essential commodities. Teachers worked without pay for several months while unemployment

rose considerably. The great expectations of the citizens in the area of education, health, and social welfare became illusory. When another general election came in 1983, it showed that the civilian government was more inefficient, incompetent and undisciplined than the military regime before it. The election was full of malpractice, ballot snatching and violence just like the one held during the first republic. These recurrent malpractices cast doubts in the minds of some Nigerians on the ability of the country to run a truly democratic government (Muhammad, 2013:88).

In the midst of these discontents and frustrations, the civilian government of Alhaji Shehu Shagari was overthrown by the army on 31st December 1983. This came as a great relieve to Nigerians who overwhelmingly welcomed the military government headed by Major General Muhammadu Buhari. Nigeria once again lost democracy as a result of the absence of Good Governance. Again, the theory of Relative Discontent applies in this scenario. Having endured military rule for thirteen years with its attendant challenges, the expectations of Nigerians were indeed very high. The resentment reached its crescendo when it turned out that the politicians were even more corrupt than the military officials. No commitment or attention was made to the application of the tenets of Good Governance and its ingredients were lacking in the polity. Caution was thrown to the winds and a mass revolt became inevitable. This discontentment was however expressed in the mass welcome accorded the military regime in 1983.

After the second democratic experiment failed, Nigerians endured military rule with its attendant maladies for fifteen years. During this period Nigeria's once vibrant civil society declined, health institutions and infrastructure collapsed, corruption was enthroned in public life, human rights violation took centre stage, and a resurgence of ethnic and religious violence was witnessed across the nation. This is why the return to democratic rule in 1999 was greeted with a great sigh of relief and once again the expectations of Nigerians were very high. The Obasanjo's administration's economic policies based on liberalization, diversification, investment promotion, transparency in the management of public funds, the fight against corruption, poverty alleviation programmes were all expected to result in a massive improvement in the quality of life of Nigerians (Uya, 2000:10).

6. Challenges to the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria

As earlier expressed in this paper, it is one thing to get democracy, it is another thing, often more difficult, to keep it, to consolidate it, to breath real life and meaning to it, to make it endure (Oyavbaire, 1992:124). With the return to civil rule in 1999 and the beautiful social and economic plans outlined by the Obasanjo's administration, Nigerians became even more expectant that their aspiration as a people will be met. The joy was even more intense when the nation witnessed the first ever civilian to civilian transmission of power in 2007 with the emergence of the Yar'adua/Jonathan and the Buhari administrations. Several administrations have come and gone the

question remains, to what extent has good governance been entrenched in the nation? To what extent has democracy been consolidated in Nigeria? It is instructive to note that the many years of elections and changing from one elected administration to the other does not necessarily translate into the consolidation of democratic practice and ethos. This paper here identifies some challenges to the consolidation of democracy in Nigeria.

Ethnic Chauvinism: from all indications, the Nigerian society is still balkanized along ethnic lines. More dangerous is the marginalization of some ethnic groups by those in power in flagrant disrespect to the principle of Federal Character as enshrined in the Constitution of Nigeria. This feeling of alienation has made some ethnic groups agitate to also have a share of the "national cake". The rise of Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) in the South East among others points to the danger the nation faces if ethnic bigotry is not addressed. (Victor, 2002:45). Democracy cannot be consolidated in an environment of ethnic rivalry and bigotry. There must therefore be an atmosphere of mutual understanding, equal opportunity for all irrespective of ethnic inclination and respect to the rule of law if Democracy must be Consolidated in Nigeria.

Poor revenue allocation: In a plural society like Nigeria, it is only the practice of true federalism and a just and equitable Revenue Allocation that can guarantee peaceful coexistence required for democracy to thrive. True Federalism will certainly entrench fairness and justice in the system but lack of it will instigate regional protest and dissatisfaction in the nation. A good example is the continuous agitations by the people of the Niger Delta region who have expressed dissatisfaction in the un-equitable allocation of revenue from the region. These agitations have over time turned violent and democracy which constitutes peace and justice cannot thrive in such situation.

Poverty: The crowning of Nigeria as the world's Poverty Capital of the world by the Brookings Institute in 2019 lends credence to the fact the poverty level in Nigeria is becoming alarming. The widespread of poverty occasioned by bad governance and poor choices of economic policies on the path of government cannot sustain democracy for a long time. According to Ake (1996:26), a society that has more beggars, parasites and bandits will certainly have difficulties to develop and peace and stability which are the requirements of democracy will elude such society.

Corruption: corruption poses a great challenge to the entrenchment of democratic ethos in any society. It is against this background that the former United States Ambassador to Nigeria, John Campbell stated in his book that corruption remains a clog in the wheel of progress of any nation struggling for the consolidation of democracy and good governance (Cambell, 2011:11). Put differently, democracy cannot grow in a society where corruption thrives. Corruption is the enemy of democracy. It is therefore very worrisome that the journey of Nigeria towards

consolidating democracy is replete with corruption cases. An indication that the hope of consolidating democracy in Nigeria can only be achieved when Nigeria can tackle the issue of corruption.

Insecurity: one of the greatest challenges to the consolidation of democracy in Nigeria is the challenge of Insecurity. Since 1999 from the Jukun and Tiv crisis in 2000 through herdsmen/farmers crisis in the Middle Belt, the protracted Boko Haram crisis in the north, the incidents of kidnapping and militancy in the south, the activities of IPOB in the South East are only indications that Nigeria is sitting on a keg of gun powder which might explode anytime. This calls for concerns as democracy cannot be consolidated in such a situation.

7. The Role of Good Governance in the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria

From the foregoing, it is clear that many societal ills and anti-democratic practices observed in the first and second republics are very much prevalent in the fourth republic and poses a great challenge to the consolidation of democracy in Nigeria. As aptly observed by Nigeria's former Minister of information Professor Sam Oyavbaire;

The problem of Democracy revolves around how to forge a developmental process that is simultaneously participatory for individual citizens, sensitive to and protective of individual rights, freedom and liberties, accommodative of multiple and competitive loyalties and generative of economic growth and distributive justice (Oyovbaire, 1992:123).

The Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria ultimately involves no less than a revolutionary overhaul of institutions, attitudes, and ideas as well as the economic, social and political restructuring of the Nigerian Society. According to Uya (2000: 21), democratizing Nigeria will be a complex, slow, time consuming, expensive and contentious process encouraged only by the certain knowledge that democracy is undoubtedly the best and efficient system in satisfying the expectations of the largest majority of the people. Certain ingredients are therefore Necessary for the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria.

8. The Ingredients of Good Governance Necessary for the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria

I. The nationality question: The proper management of the nationality question which is capable of exploding into inter and intra-ethnic violence is fundamental to the survival and sustenance of democracy in Nigeria. However, one looks at it, the pervading sense of alienation, marginalization (real or imaginary), exploitation and internal colonization must be tackled decisively with the requisite political will if Nigeria's democracy must survive. Definite programmes that guarantee equality of access, even spread

of development projects, and rapid transformation of rural communities that make irrational ethnic irredentism unprofitable must be put in place. The Nigerian political space must be so managed that all nationality groups feel a sense of belonging. Good governance demands that all stakeholders must be involved in the management of the affairs of the nation.

II. The practice of Nigerian federalism: The current practice of federalism in Nigeria, especially the proper relations between the federal, state and local government, their corresponding levels of authority and sources of funds to execute their responsibilities, is a threat to Nigeria's fragile democracy. As aptly noted by Uya, the possibility of democracy enduring in Nigeria is inextricably and intricately bound up with the possibility of an enduring federal system of government that respects and tolerates particularisms without being held hostage to them (Uya, 2000:12). The agitation for true federalism must therefore be seen as part of the struggle for the survival of Nigerian democracy.

III. Political parties and electoral politics: There is no gainsaying that the behavior and performance of the registered political parties, especially their approach to elections are crucial to the survival of Nigerian democracy, The registered political parties must never become vehicles for the articulation and implementation of ethnic, religious or regional projects and programmes and they must remain national in scope, coverage and orientation. Additionally, while serving as vehicles for the struggle for power, political parties must also serve as instruments for nation-building and mobilization in an ethnically plural society such as Nigeria.

The absence of well-organized, strong, visionary and purposeful political parties, "with the organizational depth and durable popular support for democratic effectiveness and legitimacy" has been shown to be a major cause for the collapse of fledgling democracies, especially in Latin America (Uya, 2000:14). As is already becoming evident, the behavior and antics of the political class as well as the internal organization, Structure and method of selecting officeholders and funding, are yet to conform fully established democratic norms of access, decorum, commitment to fairness, fair play, equity and justice, are threats to Nigerian democracy. Similarly, democracy cannot long endure where the conditions for forming or joining political parties and contesting elections are heavily monetized and put out of the reach of the middle and lower classes, not to talk of the masses as is the case in Nigeria today.

IV. Performance of executives and legislatures: A major cornerstone of the current democratic experiment in Nigeria is the division of powers between the executive, legislative and judicial branches of government based on the principle of checks and balances. All three arms of government must play their constitutionally defined roles effectively and appropriately for democracy to survive. It is in this context that mounting evidence of rascality,

indiscipline, corruption, rashness, frivolity and even gangsterism in virtually all branches of our government must be regarded as major threats to democracy in Nigeria. When violence, blackmail, intimidation, gangsterism and disrespect for constitutionally defined boundaries become instruments of policy in the hands of executives, legislators and even judges, democracy cannot survive. Differences there certainly will be, but how well they are managed becomes critical for the consolidation of democracy.

- V. **The media:** The media, democracy and Good Governance go hand in hand. Just as viable articulate and development-oriented media are essential for the consolidation of Democracy, a corrupt, illiterate, poorly equipped and partisan prone media is a sure guarantee for the collapse of democracy anywhere in the world. The Nigerian Media must therefore strive to sustain the ideals and practice of democracy.
- VI. **Basic needs and democracy:** Critical to the Consolidation of Nigerian democracy is the creation of an appropriate environment in which the Basic Needs of Nigerians are adequately met. These Basic Needs can be grouped into those dealing with; security, liberty, justice, public welfare, happiness, dignity and identity.

The basic tenet of the Basic Needs Approach is the creation of a citizenry imbued with a strong sense of self-reliance and control over their own lives in such critical areas as food, shelter, education and health to alleviate their poverty and underdevelopment. It is in this sense that Uya (2000:16) correctly states that "poverty is the principal obstacle to democratic development" and "the future of democracy anywhere depends on the future of the economic development". The dialectical link between poverty and democracy was aptly captured by then General Olusegun Obasanjo, in the famous Farm House Dialogue on "Elements of Democracy in Nigeria" in 1992 and quoted by Uya (2000:16) as follows:

Democracy will thrive when poverty in all its facets, is eliminated or drastically reduced. Poverty, on the other hand, will be on the run when democratic practices and ethos become the order of the day.

The failure to institutionalize democratic governance in Nigeria shows clearly that the Nigerian people have been so pre-occupied with the struggle to conquer poverty, understood here as the inability to provide or secure basic needs", that they have never had the time nor interest to generate the courage and commitment required to defend democracy, especially when threatened by self-anointed militicians or blundering politicians. For democracy to have meaning, there must be massive investment in the provision of the basic needs of the Nigerian people. These include the need of personal safety and security; deference; financial resources; electricity, water, good roads, hospitals, schools and access to political opportunities for gaining

experience in governance, especially at the grass-roots level. Poverty alleviation should thus be seen as a democratic necessity rather than a political programme designed to win votes. The point cannot be overstressed that democracy cannot take firm roots and flourish in an environment of hunger, poor health, inadequate education, poor and inadequate shelter, social injustice and physical insecurity such as presently is the case in Nigeria. As could be seen during the End Sars protest which shook the nation to its foundation, these issues are capable of causing uprising if the theory of relative deprivation is anything to go by.

9. Conclusion

In all the analysis above, this paper has taken a cursory look at the various attempts at consolidating Democracy since Nigeria's independence and their attendant failures. It has linked the absence of good governance to the failure of every democratic dispensation before 1999 and identifies some major threats to democracy in Nigeria. While establishing that Democracy in Nigeria can only be consolidated through Good Governance, the paper further explains and recommend for implementation the basic ingredients of Good Governance necessary for the consolidation of Democracy.

The Nigerian leaders and people must not think that twenty years of democracy necessarily translates to the consolidation of Democracy. Rather the seeds of democracy that are still germinating in Nigeria must be carefully watered and nurtured through Good Governance which entails hard work, patriotic commitment, sincere selfless services, and resolute determination by all, the ruler and the ruled, the leader and the led, to defend and consolidate democracy. Nigerians must bury the false hope and illusion that after twenty years, democracy has consolidated itself. Everyone should draw lessons from the EndSars Protest of October 2020.

Since the ultimate test of the survival of democracy is good governance which leads to the rapid transformation of the lifestyle of the people, institutionalizing democracy in Nigeria involves turning the economy around; redeeming the educational system; mending the traumatized psyche by replacing current disillusionment among the people with a healthy skepticism; ensuring the rapid expansion of technological bases; tackling the current unacceptable and intolerable level of poverty; transforming the severely depressed rural areas into centres of production under the control of the rural populations; and cementing unity rather than fanning the embers of disunity in the country. Only Good governance which requires improvement in the conduct, performance, commitment and disposition of officials at all levels and sectors of public service can guarantee the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria.

References

- Ake, C. (1996). *Democracy and Development in Africa*, Abuja: Spectrum Books Limited pp. 25 – 30.
- Akinrinade, S. (2006). An army of Ex-Presidents: Transitions, the Military and Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria. *Legacies of power: Leadership Change and Former Presidents in African politics*, 281-307.
- Anugwom, E. E. (2000). Ethnic Conflict and Democracy in Nigeria: The Marginalisation Question. *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 15(1), 61-78.
- Appadorai, A. (1974). *The Substance of Politics*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press. pp. 50-58
- Ajayi, A. T., & Ojo, E. O. (2014). Democracy in Nigeria: Practice, Problems and Prospects. *Journal of Developing Country Studies*. 2(2): 113-117.
- Awuudu, D. (2012). 'The Challenges of Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria' in KUBANNI *Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, Federal College of Education Zaria, Nigeria 4(3): 37-49.
- Azeez, A. (2009). Ethnicity, Party Politics and Democracy in Nigeria: Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) as Agent of Consolidation?. *Studies of Tribes and Tribals*, 7(1), 1-9.
- Cambell, J. (2011). *Nigeria: Dancing on the Brink*. United Kingdom: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, Inc. pp. 11- 21
- Dahida P. (2015). "Managing Violence and Sustaining Democracy in Nigeria: An Unresolved Agenda" *European Scientific Journal* March 2013 edition 9 (8): 90-98
- Diamond, L. (1992). *Globalisation of Democracy; Trends, Types, Causes and Prospects*. Abuja; Centre for Democratic Studies. pp. 20 – 50.
- Diamond, L. (1988). *Class, Ethnicity, and Democracy in Nigeria: The Failure of the First Republic*. Syracuse University Press. pp. 50 - 60
- Eminue, O. (2001). *Introduction to Political Science*, Calabar; Cats Publishers. p.35

- Frank, E. O., & Ukpere, W. I. (2012). The Impact of Military Rule on Democracy in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 33(3), 285-292.
- Inokoba, P. K., & Ibegu, W. T. (2011). Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) and Political Corruption: Implication for the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria. *The Anthropologist*, 13(4), 283-291.
- Gurr, T. R. (1970) *Why Men Rebel*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. p. 15
- Herskovits, J. (1979). Democracy in Nigeria. *Foreign Affairs*, 58(2), 314-335.
- Koonings, K., & Kruijt, D. (Eds.). (2002). *Political armies: The Military and Nation Building in the Age of Democracy*. Zed Books.
- Lawal, T., & Oladunjoye, A. (2010). Local Government, Corruption and Democracy in Nigeria. *Journal of sustainable development in Africa*, 12(5), 227-235.
- Modo, I.V.O (2016). *Issues in Anthropology: An Introductory Textbook*. Cultural Research Publishers, Issele-uku, Delta State, Nigeria.
- Muhammad, A. (2013), "The Challenges of Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria's Fourth Republic". *European Scientific Journal Department of Political Science*, Faculty of Arts, Management and Social Sciences, Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina State, Nigeria. 9 (8), 83-94.
- Usoro, N.A. and Ekong, I. C. (2016). The Place of Cultural Realities and Symbolic Forms among Annang People of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *South-South Journal of Culture and Development*. Vol.18 (1):166-189.
- Ojo, E. O. (2014). The Military and the Challenge of Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria: Positive Scepticism and Negative Optimism. *Insight on Africa*, 6(1), 57-79.
- Olukoyun, A. (2004). Media Accountability and Democracy in Nigeria, 1999–2003. *African Studies Review*, 47(3), 69-90.
- Oluwatosin A. (1980). "Challenges Before the New Nigerian Leaders", Daily Times News Paper, 7th January 1980, p.1-2
- Omotoso, F. (2013). Governance Crisis and Democracy in Nigeria, 1999-2012. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(14), 125-128.

- Omotola, J. S. (2009). 'Garrison' Democracy in Nigeria: The 2007 General Elections and the Prospects of Democratic Consolidation. *Commonwealth & Comparative Politics*, 47(2), 194-220.
- Oyavbaire, S. (1992). "Political Development in Nigeria" in OkonUya, (ed) *Contemporary Nigeria; Essays in Society, Politics and Economy*. Buenos Aires, Argentina; Edipubli S.A. pp.118-132.
- Salawu, B., & Hassan, A. O. (2011). Ethnic Politics and its Implications for the Survival of Democracy in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, 3(2), 28-33.
- Uya Okon Edet (1992) *Contemporary Nigeria; Essays in Society, Politics and Economy*. Buenos Aires, Argentina; Edipubli S.A.
- Uya, OkonEdet, (2000) "Civil Society and the Consolidation of Democracy in Nigeria" in *Nigeria; A Nation United; A future Assured*. Gabumo Publishers, Lagos.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (1997). 'Governance for Sustainable Human Development'. New York: UNDP.
- Victor, E. (2002), *Barriers to True Democracy in Nigeria*. Abuja: Spectrum Books Limited. pp.45-50.